

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

DEVELOPMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AN EDUCATIONAL MODULE ON
SITUATIONAL LEADERSHIP DURING INTRAOPERATIVE CRISES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Numerous studies have highlighted the importance of effective situational leadership for anesthesia providers during intraoperative crises that promotes quality care and safe patient outcomes. Literature from pilot aviation training emphasizes situational leadership, communication skills, and the use of crisis checklists to reduce human errors among aviation crises. These concepts have been adapted to highlight the role of the anesthesia provider as a leader during medical crises. However, a recent Delphi analysis has identified knowledge gaps in situational leadership among anesthesia providers. This doctoral project aims to effectively implement a video-based situational leadership educational module for anesthesia providers to improve crisis management leadership skills in the operating room throughout Southern California hospitals. The Iowa Model provided the supporting conceptual and evidence-based framework for this project. Anesthesia providers who originally participated in the Delphi analysis evaluated the completed the module and completed a post module survey indicating their level of agreement and support of the educational content.

Keywords: anesthesia, leadership, intraoperative crisis, educational module, communication skills, crisis checklist.

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Background

The operating room (OR) is a high-acuity patient care environment that requires a rapid, accurate, and coordinated execution of critical steps to effectively manage intraoperative crises as they arise (Alidinia et al., 2018). Still, despite decades of efforts to reduce patient harm and improve patient safety throughout the perioperative period, the number of deaths associated with preventable medical errors continue to exceed 400,000 deaths per year (Burden, 2020). Judgment and decision-making can be compromised due to problems with memory retrieval, fixation on an incorrect problem, or other cognitive problems due to stress (Alidinia et al., 2018). In addition, elements such as fatigue and faulty equipment design were identified as promoting provider performance failures (Hepner et al., 2017). Effective performance and leadership during intraoperative crises are a function of both personal technical skills (TS) and non-technical skills (NTS) (Andereggen et al., 2022). However, gaps in NTS such as decision-making abilities and situational awareness present a significant, and often primary, cause of patient harm; both of which present a unique challenge to acute care specialties such as anesthesiology (Burden, 2020). As a result, effective responses to OR crises as they emerge can be severely hindered and result in deviance from established guidelines (Alidinia et al., 2018).

Furthermore, the current adoption of cognitive aids during OR crises continues to remain incongruent with the consistency of use by anesthesia providers. These aids are available but underutilized. For example, recent techniques to ameliorate communication failures in the OR, such as preoperative checklists, have been found to be used in practice only 38% of the time (Allard et al., 2020). Traditional surgical paradigms have been known to discourage the use of memory aids. In addition, personal resistance to change and long-standing hierarchies that celebrate an individual's ability to "remember everything", undermine team-based care promoted

through OR cognitive aids (Alidina et al., 2018). Alidina et al. (2018) suggested that the use of OR cognitive aids does not work in isolation and highlighted a need for a supportive and successful emergency response in a complex socio-technical system. Moreover, the American Heart Association (AHA) recognized that educational activities are not consistently achieving their intended outcomes, leading to a significant decay in skills within months after the learning activity (Cheng et al., 2018).

Significance

When critical events occur, the anesthesia provider assumes the role of leading an interprofessional healthcare team while simultaneously managing a complex situation and providing medical care for a critically ill patient (Burden, 2020). Albeit, while the majority of anesthesia education focuses on TS needed for competent and safe anesthesia practice, 80% of anesthesia provider-related errors are still attributed to human error from lack of NTS and failures to coordinate tasks between individuals or teams (Paquin et al., 2018; Radhakrishnan, 2022). In the United States, a communication failure between healthcare professionals is implicated in 43% of medical incidents (Allard et al., 2020). Effective anesthesia crisis leadership and management preparation, including communication training, has continued to demonstrate significance as a determinant of safe patient outcomes. Recognizing the small risk for harm and large potential benefit, the AHA (2015) emphasizes leadership training as an essential part of advanced life support training. However, this type of training is still not widely and routinely implemented in all anesthesiology-based teaching institutions (Cindyrani et al., 2018).

Due to the stressful nature of the OR under emergent situations and even normal circumstances, poor communication, and a lack of leadership skills from anesthesia providers,

can lead to negatively impacted patient outcomes (Skråmm et al., 2021; Worm, 2013). Health organizations across the United States, specifically at Kaiser Permanente medical facilities in Southern California, are therefore focused on improving patient outcomes with the help of crisis checklists, among other leadership techniques for standardized OR workflow and, more importantly, for emergencies (Hepner et al., 2017). When comparing the use of crisis checklists, a study from *The New England Journal of Medicine* found that 23% of the steps were missed in a surgical crisis situation when a checklist was not used, as opposed to only 6% missed when using a checklist (Arriaga et al., 2013). While the use of these checklists continues to show improved outcomes for patients in the OR, a knowledge gap in adequate situational leadership training among anesthesia providers has been identified (Burden, 2020). One example are gaps among anesthesia providers identified in Southern California that involved poor situational leadership skills during intraoperative crises (Hester et al., 2021).

Statement of Purpose

In crisis management situations within the intraoperative setting, anesthesia providers are tasked with the responsibility of executing crisis checklists while assuming the role of team leader (Komasawa et al., 2018). Crisis checklists provide OR team members with helpful standardized information and specific facility guidelines for tackling patient issues within the surgical setting. However, with the help of a Delphi analysis and interviews conducted by Hester et al. (2021), of anesthesia providers within Southern California, situational leadership knowledge gaps were addressed. These gaps included deficiencies with situational leadership, an inability to properly assign and delegate team roles, and missteps in following OR crisis checklists (Hester et al., 2021). Therefore, the aim of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to effectively implement a situational leadership educational module for anesthesia

providers to improve crisis management leadership skills in the OR. The specific aims were: a) Produce a video-based educational module on situational leadership; b) Pilot the educational situational leadership module with anesthesia providers at two hospital sites in Southern California, and c) Evaluate pre- and post-intervention levels in knowledge and perceived comfort level of the anesthesia provider role in leadership during OR crises.

Supporting Framework

The Iowa Model has provided the supporting conceptual framework for this DNP project. The model, representing an evidence-based practice algorithm with defined decision points, has guided the project through the pilot phase of the practice change and continued with the evaluation and analysis phases with the ultimate goal of integrating and sustaining the practice change (Indra, 2018). Based on the Iowa Model, this DNP project has contrasted the initial and baseline knowledge gaps related to situational leadership during OR crises among anesthesia providers to perceptions regarding situational leadership following completion of the educational module in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the module. Following the Iowa Model algorithm (Indra, 2018), practice guidelines can then be modified until the change is appropriate to be instituted.

Iowa Model

The Iowa model, presented in Appendix A, is a widely-used framework that serves as a pragmatic guide to clinical decision-making and the successful development of evidence-based practice (Buckwalter et al., 2017; Titler et al., 2001). The model was used to support this DNP project, which was aimed at improving crisis management leadership skills by anesthesia providers. Developed in the early 1990s by team of nurses from the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics and College of Nursing, the Iowa Model of Research-Based Practice to Promote

Quality Care has guided clinicians in evaluating and integrating research findings into patient-centered care (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Recently, the Iowa Model Collective conducted a study that critically assessed and synthesized information and recommendations prior to validating the model as a practical tool for evidence-based practice across diverse study settings and quality initiatives within healthcare (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

The Revised Iowa Model

The Iowa model offered a step-wise, simplified algorithm that outlined the essential components of developing an evidence-based practice (Appendix B). However, although 68.4% of users of the earlier Iowa model surveyed found the model to be useful, a total of 94% were interested in a revised model (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Users of the original Iowa model identified problems in each of the 13 steps of the model, with the steps identified as most problematic being: 1) identifying a priority topic; 2) critiquing research; 3) piloting the change; and 4) instituting the change (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Efforts to revise the Iowa model resulted in a validated and simplified, linear format that was utilized for this DNP project (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

First, clinicians utilized the Iowa model to aid in identifying triggering issues or opportunities within the healthcare domain that initiate a need for change, while focusing on making changes that incorporate current, best research evidence (Grove, 2019a). The revised model simplified the problem and knowledge focused triggers to five triggering issues and opportunities, which combined triggers from both prior categories (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The triggering issues were often problem-focused and evolve from observed or experienced clinical problems and data from risk management, process improvement, benchmark scores, and financial reports (Grove, 2019a). Opportunities for improvement and to address the issues were

knowledge-focused such as new research findings and current literature, changes in national agencies or organizational standards and guidelines, an expanded philosophy of care, an updated professional model of care, or questions from an institutional standards' committee (Grove, 2019a). Two new bullets were added to include accrediting agency requirements reflective of national quality strategies such as the Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (CAHPS) survey, and initiatives from accrediting agencies such as the Joint commission (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

The second step in the Iowa model was to identify a topic that will be evaluated and prioritized based on the needs of the clinical agency, followed by the formation of a group to search for the best evidence to manage the clinical concern (Grove, 2019a). Within the revised model, a step for stating the question or purpose of the evidence-based practice project enabled a more focused approach to synthesizing the body of evidence and better informs clinicians to the next decision point of whether or not the study is topic is a priority (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Buckwalter et al. (2017) identified this step as an important decision point due to the unlikelihood that low priority projects will obtain adequate resources, support, and evidence to bring the project into fruition.

The third step in the Iowa model was to form a team, which was described as challenging by some survey respondents in the study conducted by Buckwalter et al. (2017). The selection of team members required attention to the interprofessional involvement, specific subset of skills required to plan, conduct, and evaluate the project, and had the potential to change over time (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Important responsibilities of the team included reviewing existing literature, obtaining baseline and post-interventional data, and engaging key stakeholders (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

The fourth step within the stepwise algorithm offered by the Iowa model led clinicians toward researching additional sources of evidence and appraising the evidence by weighing the quality, quantity, consistency, and risk of the studies (Grove, 2019a). Previously outlined as two steps, the assembly, appraisal, and synthesis of a body of evidence was then combined to reflect the non-linear nature of the process (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Participants in the survey by Buckwalter et al. (2017) found challenges during this step and a lack of skills for appraising and synthesizing evidence. Additional barriers to resources such as time, a library, a need for tools, checklists, and charts to assist with search strategies have been acknowledged at this phase in the Iowa model by Buckwalter et al. (2017), however it was beyond the scope of the model to address many of these difficulties and the authors ameliorated the situation by providing recommendations for additional guidance with the appraisal process within the study. The second decision point within the Iowa model followed the systematic search of literature and assessed the adequacy of literature (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Identified as another point of contention among survey participants, the Iowa model was revised to include incorporating multiple types of evidence as part of the initial evidence review, evaluating evidence quality, quantity, and consistency (Buckwalter et al., 2017). These modifications were the strongest evidence of any type to be considered prior to making a decision about changing practice while discouraging premature decisions without full consideration of risks (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

Research-based protocols, algorithms, guidelines, or policies developed according to the Iowa model were then pilot-tested and evaluated to determine the impact on patient care, personnel, and healthcare agency (Grove, 2019a). However, the pilot-testing phase of the Iowa model had the greatest room for improvement. Additionally, a failure to address necessary resources, constraints, and approvals was revealed following evaluation of the early Iowa model

(Buckwalter et al., 2017). As a result, modified details for this section included developing an implementation plan (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The revised Iowa model allowed for a range in techniques to aid in developing and piloting the practice change, including engaging patients, collecting baseline data, and preparing clinicians and materials for the proposed change (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The last decision point in the Iowa model immediately following the pilot change was evaluation of the appropriateness for adoption (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Scholarly evaluation with pilot data has guided the decision by determining the effectiveness and impact of the proposed change or continue through a feedback loop guided by the Iowa model toward revision to the implementation plan (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

The Iowa model guided clinicians toward the sustainability of the practice change (Grove, 2019a). Survey respondents revealed the greatest difficulties with sustainability (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The revised Iowa model attempted to offer solutions such as identifying and engaging key personnel in the healthcare agency to integrate the change (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Following the completion of the quality initiative, results of the project were disseminated with appropriate feedback (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

The Iowa Model Used in Evidence-Based Practice and Quality Initiatives

The results from multiple studies utilizing the Iowa model as the conceptual framework have demonstrated the effectiveness of the model in driving change, promoting sustainability, and improving the safety in the delivery of care across variety of different clinical settings (Elsabrouh et al., 2018; Fannon et al., 2021; Jannotta et al., 2021; Ram & Wilson, 2018; Wyatt et al., 2020). For example, Fannon et al. (2021) found that utilizing the Iowa model as a guide throughout a quality initiative was helpful in identifying the organizational need and served as a roadmap for tailoring aspects of the project the culture of an organization in order to implement a

new protocol using dexmedetomidine for pediatric procedural sedatives for non-intubated patients and allow for long-term sedation. Similarly, Wayatt et al. (2020) incorporated the Iowa model of evidence-based practice as a framework for a quality initiative project aimed at implementing an Early Exercise and Progressive Mobility intervention and suggested that the integration of the program was possible as a result of extensive collaboration between stakeholders throughout the planning, implementation, and refinement phases of the Iowa model.

Furthermore, Elsabrout et al. (2018) emphasized the benefits of utilizing the Iowa model in quality initiative projects due to the model's easy-to-follow methodology for using evidence to support QI initiatives within an organization, leading to the implementation of a large-scale hospital mattress switch out and resulting reduction in hospital-acquired pressure ulcers, whereas Jannotta et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of utilizing a multidisciplinary team as outlined by the Iowa model to develop a process for the administration of 3% sodium chloride peripherally. Additionally, Ram and Wilson (2018) found value in utilizing the Iowa model in lieu of other models due to the emphasis on prioritizing evidence to the most important concerns and engaging nurses, who were stakeholders in the initiative to develop a pediatric fall risk assessment tool.

Although there was a lack of specific evidence supporting the effectiveness of the Iowa Model as a framework in the context of a quality initiative utilizing a video-based educational module for anesthesia providers similar to the aims of this DNP project, the Iowa model remained an application-oriented guide to the EBP process and continued to serve as a valuable source for implementing research evidence in clinical agencies (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Therefore, the utility and success of the Iowa model justified its adoption as the theoretical framework for this DNP project.

Application of Iowa Model to the DNP Project

Based upon the Iowa Model as a supporting framework, the starting point for this DNP project began with identifying a triggering issue or opportunity for improvement among anesthesia providers in Southern California (Appendix B). By identifying the need for enhanced leadership training during perioperative crises, the project was able to move forward in the next step of the Iowa Model with a concise statement of purpose. The purpose of this DNP project was to develop an effective situational leadership educational module for anesthesia providers to improve crisis management leadership skills in the OR. Considering this problem was a priority for Kaiser Permanente as an organization, the project was advanced to the next step of the Iowa model. Given the priority status of this need for Kaiser Permanente Health Systems, an initial team was formed of three graduate students from the Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) DNP program, including a KPSA faculty member as the project's team lead, and a supporting faculty member from the DNP Consortium of California State University Fullerton (CSUF). The initial team conducted a Delphi analysis of situational leadership during perioperative crisis and identified the major concepts needed in a situational leadership training module for anesthesia providers. Two additional graduate students from the KPSA DNP program were then recruited to carry out the design and implementation phase of the project and complete the steps outlined in the Iowa Model.

An extensive review and synthesis of literature surrounding situational leadership, video-based educational module application, and implementation evaluation was conducted for the project after the formation of the project team. This step of the Iowa Model encompassed the process of creating an educational module for anesthesia providers that appropriately and effectively represented the important qualities of situational leadership. After performing a

thorough review of the literature, with sufficient evidence regarding the necessity of this DNP project and the advantages to enhancing leadership training for anesthesia providers during OR crises, the next step of the project was to develop a situational leadership education and training program that was structurally based on the work of the previous DNP team. The final step was to confirm that the educational module created was indeed what the anesthesia providers who previously completed the Delphi study envisioned. Following the steps of the Iowa Model, further analysis of the initial Delphi study, research, and results from the post-intervention seven-point Likert-scale survey was used to guide the development and modifications to the module in order to ensure its validity and applicability in addressing the identified gaps in knowledge. The final step of the Iowa Model will aid in guiding the potential adoption and sustainability of the educational module into practice at Kaiser Permanente anesthesia departments.

Discussion

In summary, the revised Iowa model was intended for use by point of care clinicians seeking to improve quality in their respective field of practice through the systematic use of evidence (Buckwalter et al., 2017). When used appropriately, the revised Iowa model was adaptable for novice to expert users and continued to demonstrate usefulness across a variety of settings, while including the patient and family values and preferences (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The ease of use and feasibility of implementing the revised Iowa model into this DNP project supported the decision to adopt the model as the guiding framework.

Review of Literature

Literature Search Strategy

A search of recent literature was conducted to identify evidence that supports the significance of competent leadership during intraoperative crises and suggests the most effective methods for providing leadership training and education to anesthesia providers. A review of the literature was performed through databases including PubMed, CINAHL, ScienceDirect, and AHA. Among the search terms were keywords such as: situational leadership, intraoperative crises, anesthesia, educational modules, e-learning, self-leadership, online learning, HeartCode Basic Life Support (BLS) learning measurement tools, and NTS.

As a means for a thorough review of the literature for situational leadership, a search was also completed involving aviation leadership training methods. This aviation literature review was conducted due to the parallels that exist between anesthesiologists and pilots, emphasized by the need for individuals in each profession to have a firm grasp on situational leadership (Gersle, 2018). Similarities between aviators and anesthesiologists include the management of passenger or patient safety during emergency situations and a command of crisis checklists as discussed by Gerstle (2018) and Lark et al. (2018). Therefore, given these parallels, an analysis of aviation situational leadership teaching methods was reviewed to provide insight into this profession's effective training and educational implementation. Key search terms related to aviation crisis management included: aviation leadership, pilot crisis management, aviation emergency training, and pilot situational crisis checklists.

For this DNP project, the initial inclusion criteria were limited to recent literature within the last five years that focused on the leadership role of nurse anesthetists during OR crises and the efficacy of online-based training. Inclusion criteria included journals published in the English

language. However, due to limited evidence and a lack of high-quality studies with high levels of evidence related specifically to nurse anesthetists in the leadership role during OR crises, the inclusion criteria expanded to include literature supporting the impact of other similar healthcare specialties, such as anesthesiologists, medical students, and physicians, during intraoperative crises within the past 10 years. Furthermore, there are limited studies evaluating the relationship between implementing educational video-based modules specific to situational leadership for anesthesia providers. Therefore, search criteria were further expanded to include resuscitation training for non-anesthesia providers. Publications that did not address crisis management and leadership or online education training were excluded from the literature review. Studies within the literature review include systematic reviews, RCTs, cohort studies, and qualitative studies. The studies were appraised using the levels of research evidence by Grove and Gray (Daniel, 2019). The literature review consists of a final total of 29 studies.

Overview

A problem within the field of anesthesia is ineffective situational leadership during intraoperative crises leading to poor patient outcomes (Burden, 2020). Medication errors, faulty equipment, and provider mistakes lead to patient harm and should be addressed throughout healthcare as a whole, including the intraoperative setting (Burden, 2020). Moreover, morbidity and mortality are associated with system failures, the failures of coordination and communication between the perioperative team, unfamiliarity with the roles of the surgical team, and a number of minor events (Wahr et al., 2013). This project will attempt to address the anesthesia provider barriers, facilitators, and gaps of knowledge involving situational crisis management.

This literature review will focus on several concepts related to adapting an educational video-based module for anesthesia leadership during intraoperative crises. The history of crisis resource management in the aviation industry and its future implication in healthcare, specifically during intraoperative crises, will be addressed. Additionally, the review will synthesize what is known and what is not known in situational and crisis leadership, the implications of online and e-modules for anesthesia education, and the effectiveness of education strategies and tools.

Situational and Crisis Leadership

A review of the literature involving the effectiveness of aviation training in situational leadership and crisis management was conducted for this project. This particular review highlights the similarities in leadership skills needed during emergency situations among anesthesia providers and pilots. Relevant studies involving a precise comparison of aviation leadership to anesthesia providers' was difficult to find in the review of literature; however, literature was found regarding pilot training methods and the similarities with training healthcare professionals in situational leadership for emergencies. Helpful lessons gleaned from aviation literature that can be applied to anesthesiologist leadership training included educational programs focused on appropriate utilization of crisis checklists, an emphasis on situational leadership and communication skills, as well as adoption of Crew Resource Management (CRM). Multiple studies (Lark et al., 2018; Lei & Palm, 2021; Truta et al., 2018) discuss the importance of CRM, an aviation training method focused on situational leadership. Truta et al. (2018) focuses their study on how effective CRM training has produced a reduction in human errors among aviation and medical crises. CRM procedures clearly translate to anesthesiology based upon the necessity for effective leadership, communication, and teamwork during OR crises (Lark et al., 2018).

With the acknowledged gaps in anesthetist leadership training, success of aviation education methods for situational leadership could provide a helpful blueprint for health systems involving anesthesia training. Lei and Palm (2021) discuss a strength of the aviation profession as it provides evidence of successful leadership training programs. However, a weakness of aviation literature is evident by differences in situational emergencies involving a smaller crew within the cockpit as compared to the anesthetists' environment of an OR.

Overall, evidence from the studies in aviation crisis management provide lessons learned for considerations in approaches to anesthesia training in situational and crisis leadership. Implementing the themes of CRM into anesthesia training through educational video-based modules within this DNP project will ideally close the gaps in the perceived readiness and preparedness to lead during OR crises.

The Impact of Situational Leadership on Patient Outcomes

Effective situational and crisis leadership by anesthesia providers can directly impact and improve patient outcomes during intraoperative crises. For instance, findings authors reported within several studies have identified a positive correlation between successful leadership instruction during situational crises and decreased patient morbidity and mortality (Wacker & Kolbe, 2014; Yeung et al., 2012). In their systematic review, Wacker and Kolbe (2014) found that explicit coordination by nurse anesthetists was positively related to technical team performances during simulated inductions of general anesthesia. Similarly, an randomized control trial (RCT) conducted by Yeung et al. (2012) revealed that teams led by leaders with the best leadership skills performed higher quality cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) based on higher Cardiac Arrest Simulation test scores. Although the study was limited by a small sample size, results still had sufficient power to detect moderate rather than small changes in CPR

performance (Yeung et al., 2012). Moreover, both the RCT conducted by Yeung et al. (2012) and the studies reviewed by Wacker and Kolbe (2014) focused primarily on surrogate outcomes based in simulation-like environments rather than actual patient outcomes, which limited the transferability and generalizability to real-life resuscitations, indicating a need for further confirmation by future studies.

In contrast, in a quantitative, cross-sectional study conducted by Chan et al. (2021), the authors presented conflicting data which suggested that hospitals with a very active physician champion had higher rates of risk-standardized survival for in-hospital cardiac arrest and were 4 times more likely to be in the top quintile of risk-standardized survival as compared to hospitals that utilized a very active non-physician champion, such as a nurse anesthetist. However, this study was limited by several confounding factors that included the presence of an active non-physician champion alongside the physician champion, suggesting that they were successful because the hospitals had leaders in both their medical and nursing staff (Chan et al., 2021). Additionally, hospitals with a very active non-physician champion may have had less administrative and financial support, which may have contributed to the lack of representation and perceived effect on hospital survival rates for in-hospital cardiac arrest (Chan et al., 2021).

Missed communication and unsafe practices contribute to significant patient morbidity and mortality (Wacker & Kolbe, 2014; Yeung et al., 2012). The results from these studies have suggested that effective situational leadership by anesthesia providers mitigates system failures by addressing delays in care during simulated emergencies. Evidence from several studies supported the importance of the anesthesia provider leadership role and its impact on improving patient outcomes, and ultimately served as the driving force for this DNP project.

Qualities and Skills of Effective Leaders During Intraoperative Crises

Effective situational leadership during intraoperative crises is a complex, multifactorial concept that is comprised of both strong, personal leadership qualities and efficient training and education (Larson & Holmstrom, 2013; Paquin et al., 2018; Wacker & Kolbe, 2014; Wahr et al., 2013). Several studies found that anesthesiologist leaders who exhibit adaptability by promptly realigning their team coordination and communication pattern in response to a new or unforeseen event engendered better team performance (Larson & Holmstrom, 2013; Wacker and Kolbe, 2014). The qualitative study by Gjeraa et al. (2017) similarly emphasized the need for dynamic leadership that is dependent on the problem.

Furthermore, Paquin et al. (2018) proposed in a systematic review that the three essential functions of a leader were to allocate roles and establish the behavioral and performance expectations of team members, establish and maintain a shared mental model among the team, and facilitate team effectiveness by monitoring the external and internal environment. In the systematic review by Paquin et al. (2018), two broad forms of leadership were identified: 1) distributive leadership, where various individuals took responsibility for micro-teams composed of healthcare staff such as physicians, physician assistants, and nurses; and 2) coordinative leadership, which was characterized by the overall management of the team effort and included allocation of priorities for the team. Specific to unstructured, or unpredictable, situations in which predefined protocols are less useful, a greater need existed for coordinative leadership to direct the efforts of the team (Paquin et al., 2018; Wahr et al., 2013). Although Paquin et al. (2018) focused on a small number of clinicians, the themes identified explored patterns of role and work in crisis situations generally, thereby allowing relative transferability of findings from the small number of participants.

Moreover, multiple studies have expanded on the essential qualities of an effective leader by postulating that effective crisis interventions were found to be ameliorated by NTS rather than TS alone (Gjeraa et al., 2017; Paquin et al., 2018; Wahr et al., 2013). NTS such as problem solving, coordination, risk assessment, and leadership represent critical components of teamwork and were perceived as the most important determinants of patient safety (Gjerna et al., 2017; Wahr et al., 2013). However, studies in favor of NTS training were limited due to the difficulty of assessing performance and providing feedback, with no single accepted NTS measurement tool (Wahr et al., 2013). Additionally, the study by Gjeraa et al. (2017) was limited by the qualitative study design which impaired the transferability and generalisability of the study to other high-risk settings. However, interview subjects were representative of a national sample and suggested that further research is needed.

In summary, current evidence suggests that there are specific, noteworthy qualities of a leader during situational crises that can strongly influence team dynamics. Incorporating these qualities within the DNP project as a paradigm of effective leadership within the educational videos has helped anesthesia providers optimally manage crises, work cohesively as a multidisciplinary team, and provide safer patient care.

Online and E-Modules for Anesthesia Education

Knowledge and Performance Outcomes Following Online E-Modules

With the goal of producing an effective leadership module, a review of literature was conducted regarding the implications of online and e-module implementation for anesthesia education. Several studies were found from the search highlighting the importance and advantages of e-learning within the practice of anesthesia (Ali et al., 2021; Chu et al., 2013; Haskins et al., 2018; Serwetnyk et al., 2018; Worm, 2013). Research from Haskins et al. (2018)

and Worm (2013) specifically compared the methods of e-learning to classroom teaching. Worm (2013) provided evidence of e-Book and e-Case learning modules as appropriate educational material for anesthesia students, showing a significant reduction in time spent e-learning as compared to classroom learning. In addition, Haskins et al. (2018) highlighted improved practical test scores among e-learning groups in contrast to scores from traditional didactic teaching methods. However, a drawback to the RCT by Haskins et al. (2018) was the low sample size of available anesthesia residents and fellows. Using non-probability, convenience sampling limited the representativeness of the sample (Grove, 2019b), with the sample size of 18 healthcare providers increasing the risk of bias. Still, although an adequately powered, noninferiority RCT was warranted, results from the study conducted by Haskins et al. (2018) suggested favorable outcomes utilizing e-learning for anesthesia provider training. In contrast, the study by Worm (2013) was limited by the concern about weak internal validity secondary to the teaching-to-the-test bias, where study groups may have been taught material specifically to address the test question (Grove, 2019b). However, the results from the RCT suggested that e-learning, regardless of format, may still be advantageous as compared to traditional classroom settings in the retention of learning.

Multiple studies assessed the impact of educational training to patient outcomes during resuscitation training and found positive results in provider response times to crises, knowledge retention, and CPR performance (Ali et al., 2021; Serwetnyk et al., 2018). A systematic review by Ali et al. (2021) expanded upon prior studies to include a third, hybrid instruction style as compared to the traditional classroom and online-only CPR training, revealing that alternative CPR training methodologies are just as effective in CPR performance and knowledge acquisition. Likewise, no significant differences in cognitive post-test attempts were found

between instructor-led BLS training, BLS for healthcare providers online, and HeartCode BLS, thus emphasizing the equivalence and value of online instruction techniques (Serwetnyk et al., 2018). The studies were however limited by small sample sizes and the availability of anesthesiologist providers to participate in the study, therefore impairing the generalizability of results to other populations (Ali et al., 2021; Serwetnyk et al., 2018). Nevertheless, the results from studies supported the concept that the use of online educational modules may be a beneficial solution to training anesthesia providers in leadership skills and aided in guiding this project.

Provider Perceptions Toward Online Training

Several studies indicated favorable perceptions of online education and training methods for healthcare providers (Davies et al., 2017; Hindle et al., 2015; Serwetnyk et al., 2018). In a survey of anesthesia providers, Davies et al. (2017) noted a desire for more online continuing medical education (CME) modules tailored to anesthetic practices. The desire for online continuing medical education was fortified by the increase in flexibility, convenience, and accessibility of training, with 80% of participants in one RCT reporting a preference for an online program (Serwetnyk et al., 2018). Additionally, one study found that anesthesia residents perceived web-based learning to be a more user-friendly alternative to traditional in-person training and demonstrated an increase in user satisfaction, retention rates, and perceptions of educational value (Hindle et al., 2015). Although one study was a cohort study, all of the studies support the notion that educational modules provided an accepted and preferred method of instruction and training as opposed to traditional in-person courses.

Taken together, studies have shown that online educational modules within a modernized and technologically advanced era of medicine had beneficial outcomes, increased accessibility

and ease of use for learners, and produced equivalent results in knowledge and performance. In congruence with the Delphi study and identified gaps in anesthesia provider leadership education, a video-based educational module was developed to train anesthesia providers during OR crises.

Delphi Study for Development and Evaluation

In the process of formulating and implementing an educational module for anesthesia providers, a Delphi study was used to provide participants with a means of identifying gaps in knowledge as it related to perioperative crisis management and leadership in order to reach a consensus view. A review of literature found Delphi studies to be an appropriate method of analysis on gathering expert views and opinions of a particular subject matter. Numerous studies highlighted the effectiveness of the multiple rounds of questionnaires in a Delphi study, which were used in an attempt to enhance a study or module throughout the implementation process (Ahmad et al., 2020; Barrett & Heale, 2020; Belton et al., 2019; Borel et al., 2021). Naghi and Salem (2021) used two rounds of Delphi surveys in their study of developing a relevant curriculum for leadership competencies involving pediatric oncologists. Additionally, in the absence of high-quality evidence, the Delphi study provides an acceptable alternative to the data-collection method (Ahmad et al., 2020). A systematic review by Ahmad et al. (2020) synthesized data from studies to develop recommendations for awake tracheal intubations by using a three-round Delphi method. The first round, which reviewed and rated a list of initial recommendations, second round of ratings in which the highest rated recommendations were selected, and third round, which involved recommendation-ratification in round table discussions were undertaken to help successfully develop the remainder of the recommendations for awake tracheal intubations (Ahmad et al., 2020).

Among the potential drawbacks to the Delphi method are the use of small sample sizes within the studies in the systematic review and the potential for bias from non-random respondent samples which are often comprised of groups of experts within a particular field (Belton et al., 2019). Still, the size and heterogeneity of the group used in a particular Delphi study can be used as a proxy to support the generalizability of its results (Belton et al., 2019). Therefore, utilizing the Delphi method provided effective group-based judgment and decision-making in the absence of high-quality evidence about intraoperative crisis management by nurse anesthetists that will guide the development of this DNP project.

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Education Strategies and Tools

A necessary component to this DNP project was a method of evaluating the effectiveness of the video-based educational modules on situational leadership for anesthesia providers. QI projects and evidence-based practices should be evaluated appropriately throughout the implementation process to ensure positive patient care (Zhao et al., 2017). For example, Arazani et al. (2020) evaluated the implementation of a multimedia module for nursing practice showing enhanced learning outcomes for participants as compared to classic lecture-style learning. Therefore, literature was reviewed on the topic of evaluation methods regarding education strategies and tools. For instance, several studies found that pre- and post-module test scores, along with participant surveys, have been found to be effective tools of evaluation for healthcare modules and anesthetists' situational learning (Hindle et al., 2015; Komasaawa et al., 2018).

The need for valid and reliable tools to measure anesthetists' non-technical performance for both initial and continuing professional development is integral to clinical competence in anesthesia (Boet et al., 2018). However, albeit a myriad of non-technical skill measurement tools have been utilized across studies, there is no single accepted instrument currently utilized

consistently in practice (Wahr et al., 2013). Many evaluation tools are designed to measure NTS within a specific sub-team, such as nurses, surgeons, and anesthesiologists (Wahr et al., 2013) and therefore require further examination prior to determining the best evidence-based tools to assess learning within the scope of this DNP project.

For example, the Oxford Non-technical Skills modified scale (Oxford NOTECHS II), developed to evaluate the NTS of an entire OR, was directly adapted from an aviation NOTECHS scale and measures skills in four domains: 1) leadership and management; 2) teamwork and cooperation; 3) problem-solving and decision-making; and 4) situational awareness (Robertson et al., 2014). An observational study by Robertson et al. (2014) established improved validity and reliability in the Oxford NOTECHS II modified scale which performs at a higher degree of precision than the original version, thus potentially providing greater sensitivity in measurement and increased reliability for evaluating the non-technical performance of a healthcare provider in the OR. In contrast, other measurement tools such as the Non-Technical Skills in Surgery (NOTSS), Observational Teamwork Assessment for Surgery (OTAS), and Scrub Practitioners' Non-technical Skills (SPLINTS) have varying degrees of strengths and weaknesses (Wahr et al., 2013). Nevertheless, the most commonly assessed measurement tool is the Anesthetists' Non-Technical Skills (ANTS), with the highest number of studies confirming the validity and reliability of the tool (Boet et al., 2018). Boet et al. (2018) concluded that the ANTS measurement tool may be the best choice for clinical assessment and feedback, which are most valid and valuable when they occur directly in the workplace setting, such as an OR. Although Boet et al. (2018) recognized the risk of bias within the ANTS measurement tool among others, the ANTS has the greatest number of measurement properties

studied and remains potentially the most promising tool to use for the assessment of NTS and leadership qualities among anesthesia providers.

Ideally, real-time observation of anesthesia providers at the participating hospital sites following the completion of the video-based educational module on leadership during OR crises would have been conducted and NTS would have been concurrently evaluated using a validated tool such as ANTS to measure changes in performance and effective situational leadership. However, due to the time constraints of the DNP project, the focus shifted toward validating the educational module for its usefulness and applicability to enhancing leadership during OR crises by anesthesia providers.

Discussion

In conclusion, this literature review aimed to identify current themes and findings related to situational leadership and crisis management as an anesthesia provider during intraoperative crises. The literature review drew comparisons between perioperative emergency management and prior studies on aviation crisis management while evaluating the applicability of the findings to the target population for this DNP project. Furthermore, existing studies on the effects of leadership on clinical and patient outcomes, qualities shared among effective leaders during intraoperative crises, and the efficacy of online learning as compared to traditional classroom settings were synthesized to guide the development of a video-based educational module on effective crisis leadership. Evaluation of study and data collection tools such as the Delphi survey and the Oxford NOTECHS II tool to evaluate the NTS of an anesthesia provider were included in determining the best evidence-based tools to assess learning within the scope of the DNP project.

The review of literature was limited by several factors: 1) There were an insufficient number of studies specific to anesthesia provider leadership during intraoperative crises that required an expanded literature search to include other healthcare specialties within various study settings; 2) Of the studies found, a large proportion were those which contained several biases or were quantitative and qualitative studies that provided low levels of evidence; and 3) No current literature exists specifically supporting the development, use, and outcomes of an online module for anesthesia leadership training. Ultimately, these findings supported a need for more comprehensive RCTs and systematic reviews with high levels of evidence to support the goals of this DNP project to effectively develop a situational leadership educational module for anesthesia providers and improve crisis management leadership skills in the OR. Nevertheless, findings from the literature review provided a foundational framework to which the DNP project can build upon.

Methods and Evaluation

The purpose of this project was to design, disseminate, and evaluate a situational leadership educational module's potential to enhance leadership during intraoperative crises. The aims of the project were to first create the educational module based on a previous DNP groups outline from a Delphi Analysis and then to evaluate the feedback from anesthesia providers following completion the crisis management training module for its validity and applicability in meeting the needs outlined by the original Delphi survey results.

Effective situational leadership is characterized by qualities such as prompt and accurate response to unforeseen events, clear communication patterns, and the ability to assess both the external and internal environment during crises (Larson & Holmstrom, 2013; Paquin et al., 2018; Wacker and Kolbe, 2014). NTS including problem solving, coordination, and risk assessment additionally serve as a paradigm to effective leadership (Gjerna et al., 2017; Wahr et al., 2013). In addition, multiple studies have demonstrated the efficacy and advantages of e-learning within the practice of anesthesia (Ali et al., 2021; Chu et al., 2013; Haskins et al., 2018; Serwetnyk et al., 2018; Worm, 2013). Furthermore, educational training in the form of videos has been demonstrated to improve provider response times during crises, knowledge retention, and performance in resuscitation techniques, and patient outcomes (Ali et al., 2021; Serwetnyk et al., 2018). Positive responses to online education and e-modules completed by healthcare providers have been highlighted in several studies (Davies et al., 2017; Hindle et al., 2015; Serwetnyk et al., 2018).

In this project, an educational module was developed and will be disseminated to the original Delphi survey participants for feedback regarding its applicability and utility to anesthesia practice. Anesthesia providers were assessed for their opinions on whether the module

successfully depicted these leadership traits and whether they feel that their educational needs were met following completion of the module.

Project Design

Initiation of this DNP project began on August 1, 2022 with the selection and approval of the current topic proposed to be developed and implemented, with a complete timeline reflected in Appendix C. A baseline needs assessment was conducted prior to the start of this project by a former group that completed a Delphi analysis with Southern California anesthesia providers. An outline created by the previous DNP project team was used as a starting point to produce the educational modules illustrating both ineffective and effective leadership qualities for anesthesia providers during several crisis scenarios within the OR (Hester et al., 2021). The outline highlighted key points to be included within each video, such as examples of poor leadership expressed as poor communication and the inability to delegate or accept limitations during a simulated surgical procedure and examples of effective situational leadership, expressed as clear and direct closed-loop communication and situational awareness (Hester et al., 2021).

Following an extensive literature review, the video scripts were then drafted by the two student nurse anesthetists within this DNP project group and edited by the project team leader. Four examples of leadership were scripted: 1) One scenario demonstrating ineffective, poor situational leadership during a “can’t ventilate, can’t intubate” failed airway situation; 2) One scenario demonstrating effective, strong situational leadership during a “can’t ventilate, can’t intubate” failed airway situation; 3) One scenario demonstrating ineffective, poor situational leadership during a rapid and massive intraoperative hemorrhage situation; and 4) One scenario demonstrating effective, strong situational leadership during a rapid and massive intraoperative hemorrhage situation. The scripts went through an extensive editing process via Microsoft Word

and were continually revised via emails between the members of the DNP project and project team lead to illustrate best and current available evidence of effective leadership during situational crises.

An educational module was created for this project to guide the Delphi participants through situational leadership issues as it relates to anesthesia providers and intraoperative crises. E-learning and educational modules for healthcare providers show improved learning outcomes specifically for crisis situations (Ali et al., 2021). The program used to create the module was “Storyline 360” from *Articulate* software. The educational module highlighted the issue and importance of situational leadership for anesthesiologists, while giving participants interactive methods of learning with the ineffective and effective videos produced for the study. Due to the importance of e-learning for healthcare providers, the situational leadership module allowed participants easy online access to walk through video-specific debriefs on weak and strong situational leadership. For this study, participants were asked to participate in an anonymous survey after completing the module in order to provide constructive feedback on the module content and themes.

Additional materials required included a simulation lab which depicted an OR at Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia, actors to play the role of the patient, anesthesia and OR staff, a camera and editing team, a computer for uploading and editing of the video, and the Articulate Storyline 360 software for the development of the module. An editing team was employed to provide professional videography and video-editing services for our films that was incorporated into the final module and accessible to anesthesia providers participating in the QI project.

After the development and editing of the leadership videos, the project intervention expanded into an implementation phase where the finalized module was disseminated to the

anesthesia providers who completed the original Delphi survey for their review and feedback. Information on how to participate in the leadership module was communicated to participants via email. Participation with the post-intervention survey and demographics survey was made available through a Moodle web link, and within the email inviting the participants to participate. Following completion of the educational training module, the post-intervention survey was made available for submission. The surveys were collected anonymously using an online survey website within the Moodle platform that allowed the participants to provide opinions on the applicability and usability of the module toward addressing the knowledge gaps previously identified by the original Delphi survey.

This quality improvement (QI) project incorporated an intervention post-survey design for the purpose of meeting the aims. A QI design was appropriate for this DNP project due to the need to provide safe, high-quality care based on the best evidence (Reynolds et al., 2021). In a typical application of a posttest design, respondents will be asked to complete a self-report measure following completion of the module (Little et al., 2019). To determine the effectiveness of the educational module, the significance of the difference of the post-intervention survey will be calculated (Little et al., 2019). The post-intervention survey design is advantageous due to its simplified assessment of data at a points in time and ease of implementation (Alessandri et al., 2017).

To guide the development of this educational module, the pre-intervention assessment consisted of a survey developed by the project team targeting both the anesthesia providers' baseline knowledge regarding their role as a leader during intraoperative crises as well as their perceived level of comfort in providing situational leadership. The initial pre-intervention survey was conducted by the prior DNP group and results were used to help formulate questions to be

included within the post-intervention survey, which was then disseminated by this current DNP project team. The post-intervention assessment measured the efficacy of the educational module and evaluated the opinions of the anesthesia providers for its effectiveness and applicability to realistic clinical settings. The Iowa Model serves as a framework for clinical decision-making and project navigation, and for the successful implementation into practice. Guided by the IOWA model, the project followed an algorithmic approach to: 1) identify a priority topic; 2) critique research; 3) pilot the change; and 4) institute the change (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

Sample

A convenience sample was used for this DNP project. The sample included the anesthesia providers who have previously answered the pre-interventional Delphi survey from the Kaiser Permanente hospital facility in the Southern California region. From the list of prior Delphi respondents, three anesthesia providers provided responses to the survey. The implementation process for this project, involving the educational video module, attempted to train each participant for enhanced situational leadership. The sample selection process and inclusion criteria involved the administration of anesthesia, including Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) and Physician anesthesiologists, and excluded non-anesthesia providers from participating.

Setting

A need for enhanced leadership training was identified at Kaiser Permanente Downey Medical Center (KPDMC) (Guinoo, et al. 2022). Anesthesia providers within Southern California were used for both the pre- and post-intervention surveys. The anesthesia providers were selected with the goal of developing a successful training module which would potentially lead to similar enhancements of situational leadership among anesthesia providers at all Kaiser

facilities in the Southern California region. The location for filming of the educational videos was KPSA within a simulated OR. Development of the scripts, the filming of the videos, and the creation of the online module were conducted in Southern California.

Measures and Data Collection

Measures to learn and improve over time allow for project members to evaluate positive or negative trends and the overall progress of a project (Durham et al., 2019). The outcome measure for this project will include applicability and utility of the educational content contained within the training module to anesthesia providers; higher levels of effectiveness of the module were reflected in results of level of agreement of five or more (i.e. 5=*slightly agree*, 6=*agree...*) and low levels of agreement were considered four or below (i.e. 4=*neutral*, 3=*slightly disagree...*) on a seven-point Likert scale. The anticipated outcome of the project was a highly validated educational module that anesthesia providers found useful and applicable to enhance leadership skills during OR crises.

Like outcome measures, the process measures have a goal that can be tracked over time (Gilmour et al., 2019). Process measures act as a “pulse check” by assessing the inner workings of the system and help researchers understand whether the proposed changes are having a positive or negative impact (Excellence Through QI Project, 2022). The process measure was the percentage of anesthesia providers who completed the video-based educational module and ratio of anesthesia providers who completed both the pre-intervention and post-intervention surveys. Balancing measures should consider the unintended consequences of the new initiatives and help researchers determine if the changes being introduced in one part of the system are impacting another part of the system (Excellence Through QI Project, 2022; Gilmour et al., 2019). For instance, the balancing measures for this DNP project included increased hospital costs to

compensate anesthesia providers for taking the online training modules or increased costs to film the crisis leadership videos utilizing a professional videography and editing team.

Instruments

A post-intervention survey helped determine whether the educational module successfully addresses the gaps in knowledge in leadership during intraoperative crises indicated by the anesthesia providers following the original Delphi survey. Project team members collected data in the form of a seven-point Likert scale. The Likert scale is one of the most commonly used psychometric scales for examining self-reported perceptions and are generated from operationalizations of an underlying construct (Ho, 2017). Using a summative model to provide an exact numerical measurement of the psychological trait or perception of the anesthesia provider, Likert-type responses are scored to yield a single value (Ho, 2017). As a result, the measurement of responses from the anesthesia providers will be item-centered, and any score variation among respondents will be assumed to be attributable to the underlying differences in their perception (Ho, 2017). For this DNP project, the measurement of applicability and effectiveness in leadership training reflected individual differences among the anesthesia providers.

Once the variables of interest in a study have been identified and defined conceptually, a specific type of scale must be selected (Taherdoost, 2019). Scaling methods are divided into two main categories: 1) open ended questions; and 2) closed questions (Taherdoost, 2019). Although open questions allow for responders the opportunity to respond to a question in detail, open questions tend to generate lengthy answers (Taherdoost, 2019). In contrast, closed questions are those in which a respondent has to choose from a limited number of potential answers and provide a more straightforward response. The Likert scale is a frequently used psychometric tool

to measure attitude in sociology, psychology, information system, politics, economy, and other realms of research (Taherdoost, 2019). The Likert scale is advantageous because it is simple to construct and has the potential to produce a highly reliable scale (Taherdoost, 2019). It will be utilized to construct the survey to assess the applicability and utility of the leadership module for anesthesia providers.

Likert scale weaknesses exist such as: 1) the potential for central tendency bias, where participants may avoid extreme response categories in order to appeal to the experimenter; 2) acquiescence bias where participants may respond to statements either agreeing or disagreeing in order to appeal to the experimenter; or 3) social desirability bias where participants may intentionally portray themselves in a more socially favorable manner through their answers (Kreitchmann et al., 2019; Taherdoost, 2019). Nonetheless, reliability and validity of Likert scales have been demonstrated to increase with an increasing number of response options, such as a three-point scale as compared to a seven-point scale. Cronbach alpha coefficients are highest at seven or more-point scales, with similar reliability results between seven- and 11-point scales (Taherdoost, 2019). Moreover, in studies assessing response preference, survey participants expressed that the use of seven-point Likert scales are more accurate, interesting, and unambiguous (Taherdoost, 2019). Based on this evidence, a seven-point Likert scale will be used in the surveys for this DNP project to assess the attitudes and level of knowledge of anesthesia providers (Appendix D). The specific questions included within the survey are derived from questions utilized by the initial DNP project team during their pre-intervention Delphi survey. These initial questions, which outlined specific educational needs, were then modified and adapted on the post-intervention survey to assess whether those gaps in knowledge were addressed effectively.

Evaluation

The evaluation plan for this DNP project included a post-intervention survey. The questions for the post-intervention survey were modified from the initial pre-intervention survey conducted by the prior DNP team to assess for changes in opinions by the Southern California anesthesia providers following completion of the module. Questions were asked regarding the effectiveness of the module at providing training and skills pertaining to situational leadership during crisis management. Feedback from these providers have generated insight for potential improvements within the module and identified specific areas to improve the understanding of situational leadership.

The results from the Likert-scale were analyzed on a question-by-question basis. Descriptive statistics recommend for ordinal measurement scale items that include a mode or median for central tendency and frequencies for variability (Boone Jr. & Boone, 2012). In the case of this project's results, the most feasible analysis was made by analyzing the frequencies of the answer responses for each individual question, and then comparing the frequencies of each response to each other to better understand trends among the perceptions of the module. The summative responses to the post-module questionnaire are included in Appendix E.

Ethical Considerations

A multitude of administrative steps were taken to ensure protection of data and compliance with the ethical requirements for this QI project. Confidentiality was ensured by having participants complete anonymous a post-intervention survey without personal identifiers throughout the data collection process. During the design and development phase of the DNP project, Collaborative Institutional Training Initiative (CITI) modules were completed with topics focused on Biomedical Human Subjects Protection and Social and Behavioral Research to

satisfy training requirements involving human subjects. Furthermore, the project was submitted for approval by the institutional review boards (IRB) of Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) through the Integrated Research Information Systems (iRIS) and California State University, Fullerton IRB. Any potential risks and benefits associated with participation in this DNP project will be disclosed to participating anesthesia providers and voluntary and informed consent was obtained prior to selecting participants for the study. In addition, data gathered throughout the project was stored on a password-encrypted computer at Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia to protect the privacy and confidentiality of each participant.

Discussion

Overall, the methods for this DNP project have been diligently formulated to achieve the creation of a quality educational module on situational leadership during intraoperative crises. Supported by an extensive literature review and appraisal process, the project utilizes video-based learning that portrays critical leadership scenarios that can be examined in the perioperative setting by anesthesia providers. Initial assessment of the module was conducted by the original Delphi Analysis group via a post-intervention survey. Validated methods of data analysis utilizing the Likert-scale responses will provide an overall evaluation of the effectiveness of the module. This DNP project utilized the methods discussed above, with the support of evidence-based practice, in order to provide QI in education and training for anesthesia providers in situational leadership.

Results

The total number of participating anesthesia providers in the educational module post-completion survey was three. In response to the first statement, “The educational module conveys themes or ideas regarding situational leadership during intraoperative crises that are applicable to anesthesia providers,” all three participants responded with “strongly agree”. In response to the second statement, “The educational module effectively provides examples of good and bad situational leadership during crises,” all three participants again responded with “strongly agree”. In response to the third statement, “The educational module effectively highlights ways to best develop situational leadership skills,” two participants responded with “agree”, and one participant responded with “strongly agree”. Moreover, two participants “agreed” whereas one participant “strongly agreed” with the fourth statement, “The educational module effectively illustrates how anesthesia providers can incorporate situational leadership in daily anesthesia practice”. Furthermore, two participants “agreed”, whereas one participant “strongly agreed” with the final two statements, “The educational module effectively clarifies who should be in control of the cognitive aid (crisis checklist binder) during an intraoperative crisis,” and “The educational module represents a length of time that is appropriate and allows learning about situational leadership”. One provider indicated in the free-write portion of the survey, “Overall, great module! Some narrations on the slides would improve the quality”. The responses from the post-module questionnaire are depicted on a frequency table in Appendix E and bar graph in Appendix F.

Discussion

Evidence exists supporting the use of online modules as an effective source of training for healthcare providers (Ali et al., 2021; Chu et al., 2013; Haskins et al., 2018; Serwetnyk et al., 2018; Worm, 2013). For instance, drawing from the Likert survey responses, anesthesia providers felt that the online module presented information applicable to their practice, which suggests that the e-learning format was indeed an effective mode of teaching for the healthcare participants and therefore consistent with our literature review. Furthermore, the responses to the educational module were overall highly favorable, with the study participants either agreeing or strongly agreeing that the module was effective in conveying specific themes and examples regarding situational leadership. This further supports the findings by Davies et al. (2017), Hindle et al. (2015), and Serwetnyk et al. (2018) that online training improves perceptions of educational value. Lastly, the average score for each question was 6.33 or greater. Based on the previously defined level of agreement of five or more on the Likert scale responses (i.e. *5=slightly agree, 6=agree...*) as indicative of a highly effective module, this situational leadership module appears to be a useful tool in aiding in improving the education of anesthesia providers.

The results of this post-module survey fall within the development phase of the Iowa Model. According to the Iowa Model, the results of the survey will be used to guide the development and modifications to the module, to ensure its validity and applicability in addressing the identified gaps in knowledge. Currently, the responses provided by the anesthesia providers suggest that there are minor changes that could be made, such as incorporating an audible narration to the module, to enhance the learning and effectiveness of the presentation before piloting the module at a healthcare site (Appendix E).

Recommendations

Based on the results of this DNP project, additional refinement and improvement in the quality and contents of the module would be recommended based on data collected from anesthesia providers after training in situational leadership during intraoperative crises. Results from the post-module survey can aid in tailoring the module toward more specific leadership areas and address more specific goals for anesthesia providers while training for effective leadership during intraoperative crises. One area identified for improvement is the lack of narration during throughout the module. This was suggested by one anesthesia provider as an improvement to enhance the learning from the educational module. Furthermore, results from the module suggest that further research on the adaptation of crisis management checklists during the perioperative period may be warranted and potentially including an outline on the specific role of the anesthesia provider in assuming the responsibility of initiating the crisis checklist within the module may assist in learning. A future goal for this project is to pilot the module at one or two Southern California hospitals in order to evaluate situational leadership knowledge among anesthesia providers. Lastly, following the final step in the Iowa Model to maintain sustainability in the education and training, it is recommended that the module is integrated as an annual situational leadership training requirement.

Limitations

Several limitations were acknowledged during this project. First, there was a limited amount of available studies that focused specifically on leadership by anesthesia providers during intraoperative crises. This lack of available research resulted in the need for an expansion of the search criteria to include studies involving other healthcare members in various critical or simulated scenarios. Many of the included studies were quantitative and qualitative studies

which demonstrated lower levels of evidence and the potential for bias due to non-random samples and small sample sizes within their studies. The weakened quality of scientific evidence, therefore, suggests a need for more comprehensive RCTs and systematic reviews with high levels of evidence to sufficiently strengthen the implications and recommendations of this project. Additionally, while the original intent was to disseminate the educational module to two Kaiser Permanente facilities in Southern California, participation from these hospitals was difficult to achieve due to the time constraints of the anesthesia providers at these sites. Therefore, after discussion with the DNP project chair and team, it was decided that dissemination and evaluation of the module would best be achieved by the original Delphi survey participants which resulted in a decreased sample size. This limitation affected the overall strength and quality of our statistical findings.

Implications

The results of this project suggest that an educational module on situational leadership during intraoperative crises is beneficial to anesthesia providers. It was well received and seen as applicable to anesthesia practice, although there is room for improvement in specific areas of the module, such as potentially shortening the overall length of the module to better assist in retention, level of focus, and engagement of anesthesia providers. However, the use of the module will help anesthesia providers better understand their role when it comes to initiating the utilization of the crisis checklist and implement effective communication during intraoperative crises.

Conclusion

Situational leadership is an important and necessary skill for anesthesia providers to demonstrate during OR emergencies. It is the responsibility of the anesthesia provider to assume

the role of team leader if the surgeon is otherwise occupied during an intraoperative emergency. However, a deficiency in situational leadership education and crisis management training has demonstrated the importance of creating an educational module to help close the gap in these areas for anesthesia providers. The incorporation of an educational module on situational leadership for anesthesia providers is a well-supported need and will seek to ultimately improve patient outcomes and provide a more robust and efficient healthcare team milieu in the event of a real perioperative crises. Utilizing the educational module as a learning tool can potentially improve anesthesia providers' knowledge and understanding of leadership during intraoperative crises in an effort to improve patient care in the operative setting.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: The Iowa Model

Figure 1

Revised Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

Appendix B

Figure 2: Implementation of the Iowa Model Revised

Figure 2

Implementation of the Iowa Model Revised

Appendix C

Table 1: Timeline of DNP Project

Table 1

Timeline of DNP Project

August 2022	September 2022	October 2022	November 2022	December 2022	January 2023
Select topic for DNP project	Meet with prior DNP group and Team Lead to discuss continuity of project	Submit draft ROL and TOE with Team Lead and incorporate feedback	Develop methods and evaluation plan for DNP project	Present project PowerPoint to Team Lead and Committee Member	Develop script for 4 crisis scenarios
Identify problem, purpose statement, and project aims	Perform review of literature (ROL) and create table of evidence (TOE)	Submit final version of ROL and TOE to Committee Member	Submit draft of methods and evaluation with Team Lead and incorporate feedback	Submit DNP project proposal	Develop post-intervention survey
Submit draft introduction and background with Team Lead and incorporate feedback		Identify supporting framework for DNP project	Submit final version of methods and evaluation to Committee Member		Film educational videos
Submit final version of introduction and background to Committee Member		Submit draft of supporting framework with Team Lead and incorporate feedback	Submit PowerPoint Presentation to Team Lead and incorporate feedback		Perform video editing
		Submit final version of supporting framework to Committee Member			
February 2023	August 2023	September 2023	October 2023	November 2023	December 2023
Continue to modify scripts based on feedback from Team Lead	Begin development of educational module	Film and edit crisis situation videos	Implement videos and revise module based on feedback from Team Lead	Finalize educational module	Disseminate DNP findings
Continue to modify post-intervention survey based on feedback from Team Lead		Design poster board		Disseminate module to anesthesia providers	
				Submit final DNP paper	

Appendix D

Figure 3: Post-Module Questionnaire

Figure 3

Post-Module Questionnaire

Situational Leadership Educational Module Feedback Questionnaire

Thank you for taking the time to review the Situational Leadership Educational Module and survey. Please answer all questions after reviewing the educational module on situational leadership.

- 1. The educational module conveys themes or ideas regarding situational leadership during intraoperative crisis that are applicable to anesthesia providers**

1 – Strongly disagree	2 – Disagree	3 – Somewhat disagree	4 – Neither agree or disagree	5 – Somewhat agree	6 – Agree	7 – Strongly agree
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- 2. The educational module effectively provides examples of good and bad situational leadership during crises**

1 – Strongly disagree	2 – Disagree	3 – Somewhat disagree	4 – Neither agree or disagree	5 – Somewhat agree	6 – Agree	7 – Strongly agree
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- 3. The educational module effectively highlights ways to best develop situational leadership skills**

1 – Strongly disagree	2 – Disagree	3 – Somewhat disagree	4 – Neither agree or disagree	5 – Somewhat agree	6 – Agree	7 – Strongly agree
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- 4. The educational module effectively illustrates how anesthesia providers can incorporate situational leadership in daily anesthesia practice**

1 – Strongly disagree	2 – Disagree	3 – Somewhat disagree	4 – Neither agree or disagree	5 – Somewhat agree	6 – Agree	7 – Strongly agree
-----------------------	--------------	-----------------------	-------------------------------	--------------------	-----------	--------------------
- 5. The educational module effectively clarifies who should be in control of the cognitive aid (crisis checklist binder) during an intraoperative crisis**

1 – Strongly disagree	2 – Disagree	3 – Somewhat disagree	4 – Neither agree or disagree	5 – Somewhat agree	6 – Agree	7 – Strongly agree
-----------------------	--------------	-----------------------	-------------------------------	--------------------	-----------	--------------------
- 6. The educational module represents a length of time is appropriate and allows learning about situational leadership**

1 – Strongly disagree	2 – Disagree	3 – Somewhat disagree	4 – Neither agree or disagree	5 – Somewhat agree	6 – Agree	7 – Strongly agree
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- 7. Any additional comments/feedback:**

Appendix E

Table 2: Survey Response Frequency Table

Table 2

Survey Response Frequency Table

	The educational module conveys themes or ideas regarding situational leadership during intraoperative crisis that are applicable to anesthesia providers	The educational module effectively provides examples of good and bad situational leadership during crises	The educational module effectively highlights ways to best develop situational leadership skills
■ Strongly disagree	0	0	0
■ Disagree	0	0	0
■ Somewhat disagree	0	0	0
■ Neither agree or disagree	0	0	0
■ Somewhat agree	0	0	0
■ Agree	0	0	2
■ Strongly agree	3	3	1

	The educational module effectively illustrates how anesthesia providers can incorporate situational leadership in daily anesthesia practice	The educational module effectively clarifies who should be in control of the cognitive aid (crisis checklist binder) during an intraoperative crisis	The educational module represents a length of time that is appropriate and allows learning about situational leadership
■ Strongly disagree	0	0	0
■ Disagree	0	0	0
■ Somewhat disagree	0	0	0
■ Neither agree or disagree	0	0	0
■ Somewhat agree	0	0	0
■ Agree	2	2	2
■ Strongly agree	1	1	1

Appendix F

Figure 4: Survey Response Results

Figure 4

Survey Response Results

